

DSSC: Data Spaces Support Centre

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Abstract

In a digital society increasingly shaped by data collaboration, individuals and organisations seek to share data under fair, transparent, interoperable and trustworthy ecosystem. This collaborative vision underpins the emergence of data spaces—federated ecosystems that enable secure, controlled, and interoperable data sharing across sectors and borders. While the promise of data spaces lies in reducing integration costs, improving data quality, and enabling scalable, reusable solutions, their realisation demands not only technological infrastructure but also robust governance, regulatory compliance, and stakeholder coordination.

The Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)¹ operationalises the European Data Strategy [1] for Data by providing a comprehensive framework to support the design, implementation, and governance of common European data spaces. The DSSC addresses the complexity of data space development through a comprehensive suite of open assets – including Data Space Blueprint, reference architectures, interoperability guidelines, governance models, and practical support tools – co-created with a broad network of stakeholders. These resources enable semantic and technical interoperability, foster trustworthy data sharing and ensure alignment with emerging European regulations such as Data Governance Act and the Data Act. By coordinating knowledge, harmonizing standards, and supporting implementation across sectors, the DSSC aims to build a sustainable, inclusive data economy in which all actors – large and small – can participate on equal and transparent.

Keywords

Data Sharing, Data Space, Data Interoperability, Data Sovereignty, Trust, Data Strategy.

1. Project information

- Project short name/acronym: DSSC
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- Project logo: To download the project logo [Click Here](#)
- Project video (optional): To view project videos, [Click Here](#)

¹DSSC: <https://dssc.eu/>

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2. Project summary

The “Data Spaces Support Centre” (DSSC) project aims to set up and operate a Data Spaces Support Centre, as described in the Digital Europe Programme, to operationalise the European Strategy for Data. The purpose of this DSSC is to facilitate common data spaces that collectively create an interoperable data sharing environment, enabling data reuse and secondary use within and across sectors, while fully respecting EU values and contributing to the European economy and society.

The project brings together associations and industry players—including SMEs—across various sectors, the public sector, standardisation bodies, regulators, researchers, related projects, and digital innovation hubs, to foster the creation of data spaces. The project consortium includes leading associations and knowledge centres in the domain of data spaces, with broad membership, an extensive network, national hubs, open-source communities, and data space pioneers.

In collaboration with a wide range of stakeholders, the support centre explores the needs of data space initiatives, identifies common requirements, and promotes best practices. By distilling, existing solutions, integrating proven approaches, and addressing identified gaps, the support centre delivers the data space blueprint as a practical foundation for building interoperable and trustworthy data spaces. This blueprint comprises common building blocks that cover the business, legal, governance, data interoperability, data sovereignty and trust, and value creation service aspects of data spaces. The Blueprint is evolving through a user-centric approach, as the result of co-creation with stakeholders. At the core of this stakeholder network are existing and emerging data space initiatives, as well as potential implementers of the building blocks. These actors form a Community of Practice (CoP) in the field of data sharing, collaboratively creating and adopting the Blueprint and its building blocks within sectoral data spaces.

One of the key objectives of the DSSC is establish a network of stakeholders that brings together all relevant organizations and initiatives involved in the development of data spaces. The diverse network includes a broad spectrum of groups and individuals. At its core is the Community of Practice (CoP) – a primary focus group that plays a central in shaping and validating the support centre’s work.

Thematic Groups (TGs) are community-driven forums that foster knowledge sharing and co-learning among DSSC stakeholders engaged in data space development. Thematic Groups are open to individuals representing initiatives or organisations that have an established relationship with the DSSC through participation in the Community of Practice, Strategic Stakeholder Forum, or Liaisons and Collaborations. Currently, there are three active groups: Business, Governance, and Technology of Data Spaces. Thematic Groups meet regularly online (typically once a month) and co-design their agendas. Given the evolving nature of data spaces, collaboration is expected to be open and inclusive. Therefore, all TG participants are encouraged to actively share and highlight their work related to data spaces.

The project also supports the Data Innovation Board in its role of proposing guidelines for common European data spaces, grounded in the Data Governance Act. The Support Centre will engage closely with the Board throughout the development of the Blueprint, enabling the Board to adopt its elements—such as cross-sectoral data sharing standards and requirements for security and access procedures—as part of its official guidelines. The final outcome of this project is the establishment of the DSSC, which will foster the deployment of common data spaces and facilitate cross-sectoral data reuse.

3. Project available results

DSSC relies on asset-based approach. To support the deployment of data spaces, the DSSC is developing a variety of assets in collaboration with its network of stakeholders. These assets serve different purposes, vary in nature, and will be delivered at different stages. Given below is the list of assets created by the project until now:

- **Starter Kit**[2]: A concise guidance document for creating a data space, offering a multifaceted perspective on business, legal, governance, and technical aspects, while directing users to relevant DSSC assets that support each dimension.

- **Glossary**[3]: A curated collection of terms related to data spaces, each accompanied by the criteria for determining whether a specific instance qualifies as an example of the corresponding concept.
- **Blueprint** [4]: A consistent, coherent, and comprehensive set of guidelines designed to support the implementation, deployment, and maintenance of data spaces. The Blueprint includes the conceptual model of a data space, a structured set of building blocks, and recommended standards, specifications, and reference implementations drawn from the data spaces technology landscape.
- **Design Principles**[5]: A robust foundation for building data spaces that are efficient, effective, and secure, while also being tailored to their specific functional and non-functional requirements.
- **Toolbox**[6]: A curated catalogue of data space component implementations, aligned with DSSC specifications and designed to promote interoperability and reuse.
- **Maturity Model**: A structured set of indicators and self-assessment tool – including a survey and data analysis framework – to help data space initiatives evaluate their level of development and capabilities, both in absolute terms and relative to the peers. The results are visualized through the DSSC Radar.
- **Co-creation Method**: Developing a data space is a complex endeavour that requires balancing business, organisational, and technical considerations while ensuring long-term sustainability. The Co-Creation Method offers a structured, step-by-step approach to help data space participants navigate these challenges, enabling informed decision-making and effective collaboration. It guides data space initiatives through the various stages of the development life-cycle, supporting their continuous evolution.
- **Radar/Inventory**[7] : A web-based tool that provides an overview of data space initiatives, including their sectors, geographic locations, and approximate life-cycle stages—from exploratory concepts to fully operational and scalable solutions.

The complete delivery plan of the DSSC project, summarising the outcomes and timeline of asset publication, is available at the following: [Link]. Related publications can be accessed via the: [DSSC Repository].

4. Relevance to ESWC conference

Interoperability is one of the key building blocks of data spaces. The DSSC project is developing comprehensive guidelines to support the creation of an interoperable ecosystem that enables seamless data sharing between participants—namely data providers and data consumers. These guidelines emphasize the use of common vocabularies to achieve semantic interoperability within data spaces. It encompasses a range of semantic assets –such as ontologies, data models, schema definitions, mapping, and API specifications – that facilitate the structured annotation and description datasets and data services. The accompanying guidelines also define robust processes for the creation, maintenance, and evolution of vocabularies, ensuring their continued relevance and unity within dynamic data ecosystem. These shared vocabularies are critical to enabling heterogeneous systems to develop a common understanding—a central theme also promoted by the European Semantic Web Conference.

The project also develops guidance on using common data exchange protocols, which define the syntax, semantics, and sequence of interactions. These protocols serve as the basis for Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), enabling applications to communicate effectively. While APIs may vary by domain, standardisation within a data space is essential for ensuring interoperability across participants and systems. The project views the networking opportunities at ESWC as a valuable platform to introduce and discuss these interoperability guidelines, given that interoperability is a core focus of the conference.

5. Value brought by the project to ESWC participants

The DSSC project brings real value to the ESWC project Networking Track in two main areas:

- **Semantic Alignment:** DSSC provides practical tools, guidance, framework to help different data spaces work together smoothly. A core aspect of this contribution lies in the application of semantic technologies, which enable heterogeneous systems to exchange data in a manner that preserves and conveys meaning. By encouraging the use of shared vocabularies, ontologies, data models, and schema definitions, the DSSC tackles a central challenge in data sharing: making sure that data is understandable and reusable by all participants—whether they are data providers or consumers. This work closely supports ESWC’s goals around scalable, semantically rich data integration. The DSSC takes an approach to interoperability that reflects the foundational principles of the European Union, blending legal compliance with a commitment to responsible innovation. This balance ensures that technological progress goes hand in hand with safeguards for privacy, transparency, and accountability.
- **Reusable Assets:** DSSC offers a large collection of openly accessible reusable assets such as the Data Space Blueprint, design principles, glossary, maturity model etc. These assets are strongly relevant to advancing research and development in distributed, semantically enriched systems. Through its two critical instruments Community of Practice and Network of Stakeholders, DSSC fosters dialogue and alignment with stakeholders across sectors. Also, the DSSC actively engages with different standardisation bodies such as World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), CEN-CENELEC, digital innovation hub, and domain-specific initiatives, fostering cross-sector collaboration and knowledge exchange that is highly valuable to ESWC conference audience.

6. Value gained by the project from ESWC participation

Through participation in the ESWC Project Networking track, the DSSC seeks to spearhead significant strategic objectives complementary to its objective of developing interoperable, cross-domain data spaces based on semantic technology. The principal goals are:

- *Collaborative Research and Development:* We plan to engage with experts in semantic interoperability, ontology engineering, and distributed knowledge representation in order to enrich the functional layer of data interoperability building block of the Data Space Blueprint. In particular, we seek to co-develop and validate our assets primarily data interoperability design principles.
- *Early Adoption and Practical Feedback:* DSSC invites participation from data space practitioners and domain-specific initiatives to serve as early adopters and evaluators of its open assets, including the Blueprint, design principles, DSSC Toolbox, co-creation method, and the DSSC Radar. Their hands-on experience will enable evidence-based tuning and sectoral alignment of DSSC outputs.
- *Synergies with Complementary Expertise and Cross-Project:* We invite cooperation with projects speaking to federated data infrastructure, linked data, AI integration, and governance controls. Cooperation will enable convergence on the common problems and reusable, scalable solutions that are transposable to European technology roadmaps and data policies.
- *Effective Dissemination:* ESWC offers a premier venue to present DSSC’s assets to a targeted and highly knowledgeable audience in the fields of Semantic Web, Knowledge Graphs, Artificial Intelligence, and data infrastructure which are the basic building blocks of interoperability. The event provides a platform to increase visibility, stimulate critical feedback, and situate DSSC within the broader innovation ecosystem

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